

Summary of Research Grant Proposal (RCN, 2022): Practice Makes Perfect? The Role of Practice in Entrepreneurs' Performance

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Primary and secondary objectives of the project

The primary objective of this project is to develop knowledge on which skills are (distinctly) associated with entrepreneurship and on the role of practice in the attainment of expert performance by entrepreneurs (i.e., business founders). This is an important undertaking because entrepreneurs often experience a pressure to perform at a high level in new business venturing, and because executing entrepreneurial tasks expertly increase the chances of success of a new venture. A secondary objective is to examine how practice and performance take place within sustainable entrepreneurship. This is important because of the contributing role of entrepreneurship in promoting responsible social and environmental change. An investigation of which entrepreneurial skills are needed in this regard, as well as how they can be developed, is critical given today's socioecological challenges.

Project summary

It is imperative for business founders to perform entrepreneurial tasks expertly in order to increase their chances of success. However, there is scarce knowledge of how business founders can achieve this expertise, partly because the field lacks knowledge on which entrepreneurial tasks—and corresponding skills—are amenable to practice. In fact, little is known about which skills are (distinctly) associated with conventional and sustainable entrepreneurship, the extent to which these skills can be the object of practice, and the role of practice in the attainment of expert performance by entrepreneurs. Given this, this project aims to develop knowledge on the practice-performance relationship within the entrepreneurship context, and to advance our knowledge on the nature and role of practice in entrepreneurship. This project focuses on two empirical contexts: entrepreneurship education and business incubation. The focus on these contexts and on early-stage business founders is appropriate because of the pressure for performance in new business venturing, and because of the need for founders to acquire and/or develop entrepreneurial skills as early as possible in the entrepreneurship process. The objectives of this project are reflected in the following research questions:

- *RQ1*: What skills are (distinctly) associated with conventional and sustainable entrepreneurship, and to what extent can they be practiced?
- *RQ2*: What is the relationship between practice and performance in the entrepreneurship context?

This project’s activities are organized in five work packages, as illustrated on the figure that follows.

Outcomes and impacts

This project has the potential to reinvigorate entrepreneurship research by connecting it to the notions of practice and performance. Thus far, studies have predominantly taken a static approach to the investigation of the drivers of entrepreneurship (e.g., human capital). This project suggests a shift from this static view to a dynamic one, where learning through practice can be accommodated. As such, the project can spark the interest of scholars in looking at entrepreneurship as a developmental process wherein practice is a crucial component. Further, this project can contribute by providing a blueprint for how entrepreneurship education can transition to action-based instructional approaches that move students to actually starting and developing sustainable businesses, and by providing insights and best practices regarding incubators’ learning environment.